

Annual article processing charges for six large scholarly publishers

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Article processing charges (APCs) were originally devised as an alternative to subscription models that could support open access (OA) publishing but have since become a financial barrier for authors and a lucrative source of revenue for scholarly publishers. APCs are difficult to track as they vary by publisher, journal and over time. Reliable and comprehensive annual APC data is challenging to gather, eliciting a diverse range of approaches to estimate and monitor APC spending. This paper introduces a dataset of APCs of six large commercial scholarly publishers – Elsevier, Frontiers, PLOS, MDPI, Springer Nature and Wiley – between 2019 and 2023, produced from snapshots collected from publisher websites and via Wayback Machine. Data includes journal metadata, collection methods and annual APC price list information in several currencies for 8,722 unique journals and 36,618 journal-year combinations. The dataset can support library collection development and scientometric analyses on APCs for gold and hybrid OA journals.

1. Introduction

In the twenty years since the advent of the open access (OA) movement, a myriad of publishing models has emerged as alternatives to well-established subscription models, contributing to the growing complexity of the OA publishing landscape. One increasingly popular approach to OA, widely known as the author-pays model, relies on the use of article processing charge (APC). APCs have proven to be a reliable and controversial business model for large commercial publishers. Frontiers and MDPI, for example, rely solely on APCs to generate

revenue. The five largest commercial publishers – Elsevier, Sage, Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, and Wiley - use APCs to supplement existing strategies like traditional subscriptions (Butler et al., 2023). Over the past decades, this model has proven lucrative for publishers not only through its generation of revenue to fund the costs of publishing but also by increasing overall profits, thereby augmenting commercial endeavours (Butler, 2023; Butler et al., 2023; Shu & Larivière, 2024). As the OA publishing landscape experienced large-scale growth (Piwowar et al., 2018), the APC model has evolved in tandem with the support of funder and institutional OA policies and through read-and-publish agreements (largely between publishers and institutions), which combine APCs with subscriptions. (ESAC, n.d.; Farley et al., 2021; Hinchliffe, 2019).

Many studies have analyzed APCs, considering aspects like the relationship between APC pricing and prestige (Asai, 2020; Demeter & Istratii, 2020; Khoo, 2019; Schönfelder, 2020), the inequities of OA models (Khanna et al., 2022; Olejniczak & Wilson, 2020; Smith et al., 2021), determinants of APC pricing, disciplinary practices, or publisher revenues (Butler, 2023; Butler et al., 2023; Puehringer et al., 2021; Shu & Larivière, 2024). These studies encountered various limitations such as incomplete data from the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) (Asai, 2023), locating historical data, gathering and applying institutional discounts and waivers, and identifying authors who pay the APC. Not only is an institution's APC expenditure not often openly accessible, but institutions employ a range of methods to estimate their authors spend (a notable exception is the OpenAPC initiative in Germany). Additionally, publisher price lists can be challenging to access, especially historical annual data, as there is a lack of transparency around APC prices (Butler et al., 2023). As a result, studies have employed a variety of methods to collate APCs and fill in missing data points, such as using an average APC, applying the current APC fee for a journal to older publications (Zhang et al., 2022), or relying on self-reported data.

These approaches serve the objectives of their studies, but risk over- or under-estimating actual spending. Given the growing use and impact of APC-based models, there is a need for reliable data that can support evidence-based decision making by institutions, funders, or consortia during negotiations with publishers or in the context of policy making. This paper introduces an open dataset of APC prices collated from publisher price lists (Butler et al., 2024) which can be used to analyze the scholarly publishing market. Below we describe the methods used to collect, process, and clean APC data for journals published by Elsevier, Frontiers, MDPI, PLOS, Springer Nature and Wiley. We then summarize and discuss the dataset at a high level, by presenting preliminary analysis and observations and conclude by addressing potential uses of this open dataset.

2. Data and methods

The accompanying dataset combines and standardizes data from the APC price lists of six large commercial publishers (i.e., Elsevier, Frontiers, MDPI, PLOS, Springer Nature, and Wiley). This data updates and expands on Butler et al.'s (2022) dataset, first used and described in Butler et al.'s (2023) study, by including annual APC prices beyond 2018 and of two large multidisciplinary publishers (Frontiers and MDPI). The dataset includes APC prices for 8,722 unique journals and 36,618 data points, so-called journal-year combinations spanning five years (2019-2023). Column headings, example values, and descriptions of each field are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables in the APC dataset.

Variable name	Description	Example value
unique_id	The unique identification number assigned to each journal in this dataset.	15
Publisher	The publisher of the journal in the particular year.	Springer Nature
ISSN_1	The first ISSN of the journal, usually but not always the electronic ISSN.	1572-9087
ISSN_2	The second ISSN of the journal; if provided usually but not always the print ISSN.	0252-9602
Journal	The title proper of the journal.	Acta Mathematica Scientia
OA status	The open access status of the journal, indicated by the publisher or journal website.	Hybrid
APC_currency* * for each of following currencies: USD, EUR, GBP, JPY, CHF, CAD	The article processing charge value as provided by the publisher or converted into each respective currency.	APC_USD=2,780
APC_currency_originalORconverted	This field indicates whether the respective currency originally derived from publisher price lists or converted from another currency using an annual conversion rate.	original
APC_date	The date of the published pricelist from which the APC value was taken.	2021-02-01
APC_year	The year of the published pricelist from which the APC value was taken.	2021
APC_source	The source of the APC pricelist data.	Publisher website
Collector	The collector of the APC pricelist data.	N. Schoenfelder
Comment	Further contextual or significant details.	Journal transferred from Elsevier to Springer Nature in 2019

2.1. Data sources

APC prices were captured from several sources and in various formats over five years. Annual price lists were regularly downloaded between 2019 and 2023 from publisher websites by one of the authors (NS). These price lists were typically provided in downloadable PDFs, structured XLSX files, or displayed as HTML on publisher websites and contained information such as ISSNs, journal title, OA status, APC list price, and currency. We compiled these price lists, cleaned the data, and added key missing information such as ISSNs to produce a first version of a dataset which is available openly for reuse as Butler et al. (2024) on Zenodo. When compiled price lists were not made available on publisher websites (such as Frontiers), APCs were scraped from individual journal web pages. While other surveys conduct data collection of APC list prices in January of each year (Pollock & Staines, 2024), ours is based on whichever price list was published or collected nearest to June of each year—the time of year for which we were able to identify a price list most consistently.

2.2. Data cleaning and metadata enrichment

We assigned a unique identifier to each journal title. Unique IDs range from 1 to 9010 and merge various spelling variations of the same journal, if identified. Unique IDs were not assigned in any particular order and some numbers were removed or added during data cleaning. The numbers are for dataset internal identification only and do not correspond to external identifiers.

Most publisher price lists include at least one ISSN, but do not always specify whether the number provided corresponds to the print (pISSN) or electronic (eISSN). Therefore, the dataset does not make that distinction either and, instead, has two ISSN columns (ISSN_1 and ISSN_2). In cases where publishers provide a single ISSN, we assign it to ISSN_1; in cases where publishers provide both an eISSN and a pISSN, we assign the eISSN to ISSN_1 and the pISSN to ISSN_2. All ISSNs were standardized to include a hyphen after the first 4 digits. In several cases, the same ISSN was assigned to more than one unique ID, for example journal name variation, errors in the price lists, journal transfers between publishers or OA status change. For example, there were 40 instances of ISSNs being incorrectly attributed to journals (see data cleaning notes in the dataset). Five instances of misassignment were attributed to Wiley journals and the remaining 35 to Springer Nature journals. Incorrect ISSNs in the dataset were verified as matching information provided in the original price lists. We assume publisher error through the misattribution of ISSNs to journals in their price lists. Correct ISSNs (when found) were located from journal websites and updated for each entry in the dataset. We manually checked and corrected all issues so that an ISSN was only assigned to one unique journal ID.

We sometimes found more than one publisher assigned to the same journal. When an announcement on a journal, publisher or society website confirmed that the journal transferred between publishers, we made note of this in the comment section. A journal that transferred from one publisher to another will still have the same unique ID. In rare cases, the transfer occurred during a calendar year and we have two APCs for the same year, one for each publisher. For example, *Acta Mathematica Scientia* (see Table 1) transferred from Elsevier to Springer in 2019. Similarly, if a journal flipped between OA status (e.g., from hybrid to gold or vice versa), we have two APCs per unique ID per year, one for hybrid and one for gold. Such a flip is also noted in the comment section. For example, Springer Nature's *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Medicine* (unique_id=5723) and Wiley's *Ecography* (unique_id=7465) both flipped from hybrid to gold in 2021.

In some cases, multiple entries appeared in a year for the same journal based on journal name variations. In these cases, duplicate entries were removed, with the entry using the journal’s title proper (as noted on publisher websites) kept in the dataset. We cleaned the dataset for spelling variations in journal titles (e.g. titles that were missing apostrophes or “the” preceding their title), matching titles by ISSN. Spelling variations occur in annual price lists, and publishers do not consistently use diacritics from year-to-year (e.g., Spanish, French, German). Details of these variations can be found in the “data cleaning notes” of the published dataset.

Publishers provided APCs in different currencies, with many publishers providing fees in multiple currencies. We therefore decided to keep APCs in all currencies provided and indicated for each fee whether it was original or converted. In order to allow analysis across journals (and in different currencies), we filled gaps by converting between currencies using respective annual average conversion rates retrieved from ofx.com. Our analysis below is based on prices in USD, since this was the most frequently provided currency at 92% of the 36,618 journal-year combinations. The remaining 8% without USD original fees were converted from APCs provided in CHF, EUR or GBP.

3. Overview of the dataset and preliminary results

In this section we present a statistical summary of the APC dataset, including the unique number of journals per publisher per year (Table 2) as well as a preliminary analysis of the list prices, including distributions per publisher, year and OA status as well as annual trends.

Table 2. Number of unique journal titles by publisher, 2019-2023

Year	Elsevier	Frontiers	MDPI	PLOS	Springer Nature	Wiley
2019	2,260	61	205	7	2,568	1,542
2020	2,292	80	272	7	2,691	1,610
2021	2,672	108	368	12	2,715	1,659
2022	2,550	148	405	12	2,723	1,667
2023	2,704	221	427	12	2,725	1,896

There are a total of 1,109 journal-year combinations with missing APC information, which are attributed to Elsevier, MDPI, and Springer Nature, and 1 assigned to Wiley owing to a per-page fee. 123 of the 36,618 journal-year combinations list an APC of \$0 or indicate that publishing in the journal was free to authors. For the remaining xx journal-year pairs that listed an APC above \$0, fees ranged from \$150 for Elsevier’s *Materials Today: Proceedings* between 2019 and 2021 to \$11,690 for 37 *Nature* journals in 2023.

As shown both in the violin plots in Figure 1 and the line graph of average APCs in Figure 2, amongst the publishers with both hybrid and gold journals (Elsevier, Springer Nature, Wiley), we find that on average hybrid APCs are higher than gold fees, as has been extensively shown in the literature (Bakker et al., 2017; Björk & Solomon, 2014; Butler et al., 2023; Pinfield et al., 2016; Solomon & Björk, 2012). Wiley has the highest APCs on average among hybrid journals and also ranks amongst the highest gold APCs, just behind PLOS. Elsevier and Springer Nature have the largest suite of journals, and expectedly, a broader distribution of prices than other publishers. It is also apparent that over time, most publishers pricing scales either remain constant, or increase over the five-year period 2019-2023 with the exception of Wiley gold journals, which decline in 2023. This decline might be affected by Wiley’s acquisition of Hindawi.

Figure 1: Violin plot showing the number of annual APCs (USD) per journal per publisher per OA status, 2019-2023.

For Frontiers, MDPI and PLOS which exclusively use the gold publishing model, PLOS has the highest average APC price. However, one needs to consider that PLOS only publishes 12 journals, while Frontiers and MDPI are represented with 221 and 431 journals in our dataset. It is striking that MDPI has by far the lowest APCs and that in 2019 74% of the journals charged a fee of \$1,007 (=1,000 CHF). However, similar to PLOS, MDPI then increases fees of some journals in 2021 to provide more of a range of price points. Frontiers seems to show an almost opposite trend with more spread in 2019 and a focus on \$2,125 (63%) in 2023.

Figure 2. Average gold and hybrid APC list prices per publisher for APC > \$0.

4. Discussion

This paper introduces an open dataset of APC prices of six publishers for five years (Butler et al., 2024) with a variety of affordances, not least the capacity to facilitate estimates of APC expenditure, which have often proven challenging to collect, and analyses of the APCs charged by scholarly publishers, which have proven difficult to collate. Our process for gathering and processing this data reveals several challenges associated with accessing and providing comprehensive and accurate information from publisher price lists. Producing an aggregate APC dataset with substantial coverage over time was resource intensive, requiring a large amount of cleaning and standardization. Data taken directly from publisher pricelists had errors (e.g., incorrect title errors, ISSN, and missing APCs), and we discovered inconsistencies in how publishers made their data available (e.g., price list format varying year to year) or the way in which prices were presented. Add-on charges, such as rapid service fees (RSF), increasingly on offer from large publishers, present an additional layer of complexity for cost estimation. For hybrid journals, RSF fees are often charged in addition to an APC. For some gold journals, RSF is presented in lieu of an APC, making them essentially equivalent. Kumar et al. (2018) appropriately discuss these issues in relation to publications' legitimacy, calling for journals to disclose their policies and processes, including OA options, and publication fees in an easily accessible and transparent manner through solicitation emails, author guides, and manuscript submission systems. Our preliminary analysis of this new dataset was based on the information provided in the original publisher price lists, which still possess gaps and may include inaccuracies.

This dataset yields interesting findings; overall, fees for hybrid journals are higher than gold and rise annually, demonstrating the lucrateness of the model, and why publishers have adopted it at such scale. Moreover, as past studies have shown, APCs are increasing annually beyond the rate of inflation, reifying that APC pricing is not always reflective of sustainable publishing costs, but rather for calling into question the supposed commitment to openness and knowledge equity (Grossmann & Brembs, 2021; Khoo, 2019; Morrison, 2020). It should be noted that the publishers included in our dataset have different marketing strategies and portfolios. For example, Elsevier tends to charge a lower APC for their gold journals than Springer Nature and Wiley, but they tend to rely on the publication volume associated with their hybrid journals (Butler et al., 2023). On average, MDPI charges a lower APC for gold than the other publishers, but MDPI may use a different strategy, such as relying on large publication numbers and special issues (Hanson et al.; Brainard, 2023).

4.1. Limitations

This dataset possesses limitations relating to its methodological approach and the accuracy of its data. We relied on information provided by publishers in their price lists, potentially reproducing their inaccuracies. We minimized enhancement of the dataset (e.g., filling gaps in missing APCs, or OA status), and instead focused on processing the data into a structured, useable format with consistent metadata. This initial version of the dataset aims to accurately reflect information provided by publishers. Incomplete data (e.g., missing APC fee and OA status) will be filled in future versions of the dataset.

5. Conclusion and outlook

This dataset offers a range of potential applications for analyses, including, but not limited to, estimating APC spending, supporting collections development, or understanding the cost effectiveness of read-and-publish agreements. While it can support practice in institutional libraries in such ways, from the perspective of research, this dataset can also aid in framing further potential areas of inquiry: its data can help all stakeholders engaged in aspects of scholarly publishing determine what questions should be asked by enhancing available data which holds implications for what can be asked.

Future versions will aim to supplement missing APC data and verify journal status through manual curation and verification. We also hope to identify the subset of gold OA journals that could be considered diamond OA (Simard et al., 2024).

Open science practices

The APC dataset introduced and analyzed in this paper will be available on Zenodo in May 2024 at the following URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11043691>.

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Author contributions

L-A.B.: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing; M.H.: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing; N.S.: Data curation, Methodology, Validation, Writing—review & editing; E.S.: Data curation, Methodology, Writing—review & editing; J-P.A.: Data curation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing—

review & editing; S.H.: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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